

SLE, The Stealthy Culprit Behind Jejunitis: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT/INTRODUCTION

Systemic Lupus Erythematosus [SLE], is a chronic autoimmune disease affecting 0.1-0.5% of the global population. Patients usually present with skin rashes, polyarthritis, myalgia, and fatigue. Rarely, patients present with increased photosensitivity, seizures, psychosis, oral ulcers, pleuritis, pericarditis. Here we report a patient, with one such unusual presentation of SLE flare affecting the GI tract.

Keywords: Systemic Lupus Erythematosus [SLE]; Jejunitis; Skin rashes

DESCRIPTION

A 28-year-old female with PMHx of SLE (+ANA 1:5120, +SSA, +Smith/RNP, +dsDNA), scleroderma, myositis, urticarial vasculitis, HTN, presented with severe, diffuse abdominal pain associated with vomiting for 2 days. Initial vitals and labs were within limits. CT abdomen showed marked mucosal and bowel wall thickening, limited throughout the jejunum with moderate dilatation without a transition zone and moderate ascites. On day 2, she developed mild angioedema and hives. She has a h/o 2 ICU admissions for acquired angioedema with airway compromise in association with her SLE flares. Her airway was protected. Stat labs showed normal lactate levels ruling out ischemia/vasculitis. Enteric pathogen panels, EBV, CMV, HIV, and H.pylori panels were negative thereby ruling out infectious etiology. Ascitic fluid paracentesis and analysis ruled out atypical and fungal causes. Rheumatology suggested starting the patient on high-dose steroids along with hydroxychloroquine. Her condition improved, and abdominal pain resolved gradually with therapy. Hence diagnosed with SLE-related Jejunitis, a rare initial SLE flare presentation.

DISCUSSION

Jejunitis remains an uncommon SLE flare-up presentation accounting to only 1% of patients presenting with abdominal pain and concurrent SLE. The exact pathophysiology is likely due to immune complex deposition causing microvascular lesions resulting in ischemia.

Patients typically present with nonspecific GI symptoms. Routine lab work typically shows pancytopenia, reduced C3,C4 and proteinuria. Diagnosis is typically made on a CT scan which shows focal or diffuse bowel wall thickening with abnormal wall enhancement(target sign), engorgement of mesenteric vessels with an increase in number(Comb's sign), hyperattenuation of mesenteric fat, and ascites.^[2]

Despite a challenging diagnosis, the disease is generally reversible and responsive to steroids. Cyclophosphamide(CYC) or mycophenolate mofetil(MMF) can be added in steroid-unresponsive cases. Maintenance therapy is with hydroxychloroquine (HCQ), MMF, azathioprine (AZA), or low-dose corticosteroids. In certain recurrent forms MMF, AZA, CYC, and rituximab have been used with success.^[3,4] Thus, SLE gastroenteritis must be considered a differential diagnosis, especially in a patient with an established SLE or other autoimmune disease. Early detection and treatment can easily prevent SLE patients from catastrophic complications including bowel perforation and peritonitis, thereby reducing mortality.

CT Abdomen showing -Diffuse wall thickening and mucosal prominence throughout multiple loops of the small bowel. This appears to be predominantly involving the jejunum.

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